

Studies on Some Organometallic Compounds of Pt(O) and Rh(I)

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Starting from $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$, three new platinum(O) complexes, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{ETU})_2]$ have been prepared. Similarly, a new Rh(I) complex, $[\text{Rh}(\text{ETU})_2(\text{P}\phi_3)\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been prepared from the complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ in benzene medium. The oxidation states of the metal ions in these complexes have been checked by iodometric titration. Infrared spectra of the complexes, recorded in the range of $4000 - 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicate that $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2]$ may be octahedral, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{ETU})_2]$ may be tetrahedral and $[\text{Rh}(\text{ETU})_2(\text{P}\phi_3)\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may have a square planar structure. Metal-ligand vibrations have also been assigned. The study indicates that $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ undergo substitution reaction in benzene medium and all but one bonded $\text{P}\phi_3$ groups are replaced by ethylene thiourea (ETU) molecule. In all the complexes, the ETU molecule is bonded to the central metal ion through sulphur only.

It is known that d^{10} tetrahedral complexes of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ behave in such a way in solution that they add up covalent molecules oxidatively to form d^8 -octahedral complexes. However, cryoscopic¹ and nmr² data indicate that the reaction of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ in solution is somewhat complicated and oxidative addition is not the only type of reaction that can occur. It was observed³ that replacement reaction occurs when a benzene solution of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ is treated with 1-substituted tetrazoline-5-thione and two of the $\text{P}\phi_3$ groups are replaced by two molecules of 1-substituted tetrazoline-5-thione bonded through sulphur, and tetrahedral complexes are formed. However, all the four $\text{P}\phi_3$ groups of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ could not be replaced. The displacement of $\text{P}\phi_3$ group in $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ complex in benzene medium has also been studied⁴. The $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ dissociates in benzene to give a coordinatively unsaturated 3-coordinated species^{5,6} which acts as both an electrophile and a nucleophile. It also abstracts CS-group from CS_2 to give *trans*- $(\text{P}\phi_3)_2$ - $\text{Rh}(\text{CS})\text{Cl}^{\tau,8}$. Ethylene thiourea (ETU) replaces two $\text{P}\phi_3$ group of $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ to produce $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex. In the present paper physico-chemical investigations such as conductometric, magnetic, far and near infrared spectroscopic and iodometric titration data of all the Rh(I) and Pt(O) complexes are reported and tentative structures for the Pt(O) and Rh(I) complexes suggested.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. Ethylene thiourea⁹, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]^{\tau,10}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]^{\tau,11}$ were prepared by literature methods.

1. Preparation of ethylenethiourea tetraquo triphenylphosphine platinum(O), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$:

This complex was prepared starting from $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$, prepared according to Malatesta *et al*¹⁰. A benzene solution of the complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ was mixed with a benzene solution of ethylene thiourea in 1:1 molar ratio. The mixture was heated on a water bath and the volume was reduced to about 10 ml. This solution precipitated a yellow complex, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, which was filtered, washed with ordinary ice-cold benzene and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . (Found: C, 39.8; H, 4.0; N, 5.1; Pt, 30.9. Calcd.; C, 39.9; H, 4.3; N, 4.5; Pt, 31.2%).

2. Triethylenethiourea triphenylphosphine platinum(O), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2]$: This complex also was prepared starting from $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$. $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ (1.0 m mole) was dissolved in hot benzene (20 ml) and the resulting solution was filtered into a filtered hot solution of ethylenethiourea (3.0 m mole) in benzene (30 ml). The mixture was heated on a water bath till the volume was reduced to about 10 ml. On cooling, brownish black crystals of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2]$ separated out, which were filtered, washed with benzene and dried at 110° . (Found: C, 42.2; H, 4.3; N, 11.3; Pt, 25.0. Calcd.; C, 42.4; H, 4.3; N, 11.0; Pt, 25.7%).

3. Pentaethylenethiourea triphenylphosphine platinum(O), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$: This complex also was prepared starting from $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$. A hot benzene solution of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ was mixed with a hot benzene solution of ethylene thiourea in 1:5 molar ratio. The mixture was heated on a water bath till the volume was reduced to 10 ml. A green precipitate of the complex was obtained on cooling, which was washed with cold benzene and dried over CaCl_2 in a desiccator. (Found: C, 40.80; H, 5.1; N, 15.1. Calcd.; C, 40.98; H, 4.7; N, 14.5%).

4. Chlorodiethylenethiourea triphenylphosphine rhodium(I) hexahydrate, $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

This complex was prepared starting from the complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ described by Wilkinson *et al*¹¹.

A hot benzene solution of $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ was mixed with a hot solution of the ligand in benzene in 1 : 3 molar ratio. The mixture was heated on a water bath till the volume was reduced to about 20 ml. A brown precipitate of the complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained on cooling, which was filtered, washed with cold benzene and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . (Found : C, 40.7 ; H, 5.6 ; N, 6.9 ; Rh, 14.0 ; Cl, 4.8 Calcd. ; C, 40.5 ; H, 5.5 ; N, 7.6 ; Rh, 14.5 ; Cl, 5.1%).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate the stoichiometry of the complexes as $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All the complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide and are found to be nonconducting in this solvent. They all are diamagnetic as Pt(O) is d^{10} -system and Rh(I) is d^8 -system. Rh(I) complex decolorises a violet solution of iodine in CCl_4 and suggests that it is a Rh(I) and not a Rh(III) complex. Hence dsp^2 hybridisation is possible for Rh(I) ion giving rise to square planar diamagnetic complexes^{12,13}. Oxidation states of metal ions in the Pt(O) and Rh(I) complexes were determined iodometrically⁸.

Infrared spectra : A comparison of infrared spectral bands of triphenylphosphine, ethylenethiourea and corresponding Pt(O) and Rh(I) complexes indicates the following.

A very broad and strong band centred at 3400 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes indicates the presence of coordinated as well as lattice water molecules¹⁴⁻¹⁶ in these complexes. This observation is further supported by the presence of broad medium bands at 1658 and 1625 cm^{-1} corresponding to δ -OH mode of vibration^{17,18} and 468 and 855 cm^{-1} due to librational and out of plane modes of vibrations of water molecules, respectively.

A very weak absorption band at 1620 and 1598 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complexes $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$ may be due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ mode of coordinated $\text{P}\phi_3$. In $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ complex, the band at 1598 cm^{-1} is broad medium because it has contribution from $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ mode of coordinated $\text{P}\phi_3$ as well as $\delta\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mode of coordinated water molecule. A strong band at 1435 , medium bands at 755 , 725 , strong bands at 695 and 545 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Rh(I) complex indicate the presence of coordinated $\text{P}\phi_3$. The νNH band of ethylenethiourea is observed at 3250 cm^{-1} which appears at 3240 , 3248 , 3200 and 3240 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes, respectively. The decrease of 50 cm^{-1} in the position of νNH and the quite broad nature of this band in $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ complex may be due to the presence of intense hydrogen

bonding. However, in the other Pt(O) and Rh(I) complexes, the small change in the position of νNH band indicates that coordination has not taken place through NH_2 nitrogen of ethylenethiourea molecule.

The weak absorption band at 2570 cm^{-1} in ethylene thiourea, which is assigned to νSH disappear in all Pt(O) and Rh(I) complexes indicate that the thione form of the ligand might take part in coordination through sulphur. It is further supported by the red shift of thioamide-IV, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ band¹⁹⁻²² of ethylenethiourea from 685 to 670 cm^{-1} (shoulder) in Pt(O) complexes, and 620 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex. The thioamide band II is observed at 1200 cm^{-1} as a medium band in the ir spectra of ethylenethiourea. This band, having main contribution²³ from 30% νCN , 36% $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ and 24% $\delta\text{N}-\text{H}$, appears as a strong band in the spectra of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$ at slightly high position (1213 cm^{-1}), but gets split in the spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{OH})_3]$ and the split bands are observed at 1240 and 1188 cm^{-1} . This change may be due to coordination of ethylene thiourea to Pt(O) through sulphur, resulting in the increase in CN bond order as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Two medium bands are observed at 1128 and 1102 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ complexes. However, these two bands are almost of negligible intensity in the spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$. These bands, therefore, may be due to the octahedral symmetry of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ which are almost absent from the tetrahedral complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$.

Similarly, medium bands are observed at 750 and 728 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of both the complexes, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ but these are almost absent in the spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$. This difference may also be due to octahedral symmetry of the former two complexes and tetrahedral symmetry of the latter.

Pt(O) complexes containing four coordinated monodentate ligands are generally tetrahedral²⁴⁻²⁷. Thus, a tetrahedral structure (Fig. 2) may be suggested for $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_3]$ complex.

Similarly, on the basis of the above observations the octahedral structures (Figs. 3 and 4) may be assigned to $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})_5]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{ETU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$

Fig. 4. Octahedral structure of $[Pt(P\phi_3)(ETU)(OH_2)_4]$.

Square planar structure (Fig. 5) $[Rh(P\phi_3)(ETU)_2Cl]$ may also be suggested on the basis of its diamagnetism and infrared spectrum. That the

Fig. 5. Square planar structure of the Rh(I) complex.

structure (b) is the correct one is deduced on the basis of metal-ligand vibrational bands in far infrared region as discussed below.

Metal ligand vibrations: In the far infrared spectrum of $[Pt(P\phi_3)(ETU)_3]$ and $[Pt(P\phi_3)(ETU)_5]$ complexes, new bands are observed at 428 (vw) and 345 cm^{-1} (medium) which are assigned to ν_{Pt-P} and ν_{Pt-S} modes of vibration. ν_{Pt-OH_2} , ν_{Pt-S} and ν_{Pt-P} bands are observed at 468 (vw), 328 (m) and 428 cm^{-1} (vw) in the spectrum of $[Pt(P\phi_3)(ETU)(H_2O)_4]$ complex. The ν_{Pt-P} assignment is in good agreement with the assignment of Goggin, Goodfellow and others²⁸⁻³⁰.

The new broad shoulder at 380 cm^{-1} , two bands of doublet at 355 (m) and 320 cm^{-1} (m) and a smaller shoulder at 290 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{Rh-P}^{31,32}$, $\nu_{Rh-S}^{33,34}$ and ν_{Rh-Cl}^{35} mode of vibrations, respectively in $[Rh(P\phi_3)(ETU)_2Cl] \cdot 6H_2O$ complex. Since only one ν_{Rh-P} , two ν_{Rh-S} and one ν_{Rh-Cl} bands are observed, the configuration [Fig. 5(b)] having two ETU molecule at *cis* positions and the Cl *trans* to one ETU may be the most probable structure of $[Rh(P\phi_3)(ETU)_2Cl] \cdot 6H_2O$. The lower position of ν_{Rh-Cl} may be due to the strong *trans* effect of ethylene thiourea.

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